

Applications of spatial arithmetic in explaining some current concepts and laws of physics.

1) Time is Space. Proposed unit of spatial value S

As mentioned in the previous article, time is space. Measuring the passage of time is essentially measuring the change in the total spatial value created throughout the universe (cumulative spatial value change) relative to the observational frame of reference.

Because time is space, time and space can share a common unit of measurement. Here, I propose the unit of space as S, with $1 S = 1 s^2$. Với hệ số trượt $k_t = k_s / c^2$, it means $1 S = 1 s^2 = 1 c^2 \text{ km}^2$.

Example: An object moves at a speed of 300 km/s. In 3 seconds, it travels a distance of 900 km.

Convert to spatial units as follows: Time the system is at rest $t = 3s \Rightarrow t^2 = 9s^2 = 9S$ (The total spatial variation of the stationary system is 9 S).

In terms of space: The object traveled a distance of 900 km $\Rightarrow x^2 = (900 \text{ km})^2 = (900 / 300.000)^2 S = 0,003^2 S$.

This is the spatial value created by the moving object in 3 seconds. The total change in the spatial value across the entire universe created by the moving object is: $9 S - 0,003^2 S$

Measuring spatial value is extremely important. Differences in the accumulation of spatial (time) value make time and space different for each object and phenomenon (frame of reference), and therefore affect the process of movement of objects and phenomena (for example, human lifespan is related to the process of accumulating spatial value). We can absolutely develop technology to track the accumulation of spatial (time) value, which will bring enormous benefits to humanity. Just as understanding the law that time is space, the mechanism of generating spatial value will bring extremely significant applications to humanity.

2) Formula for calculating velocity.

From the descriptions above, we can see that velocity essentially reflects the ratio of the spatial value created by a moving object to the cumulative change in the total spatial value relative to a stationary system.

We have: $v = x / t \Leftrightarrow v^2 = x^2/t^2$. I suggest the concept $V = v^2 = x^2/t^2$

Returning to the example above, we have $V = v^2 = x^2/t^2 = 0,003^2 \text{ S} / 9 \text{ S} = 0,003^2 / 9$.

This is the rate of the spatial value created by the moving object occupies $1/1,000,000$ of the accumulated spatial value of the stationary system.

3) Formula $E = mc^2$

This formula reflects energy compression (spatial value). Here, I propose 1 unit of energy = c^2 . Thus, mass is the number of compressed energy units. In each second, the energy unit generates a spatial value corresponding to a distance of c km. That is, the accumulated spatial value of this energy unit is completely transformed into distance through its movement. 1 S of accumulated energy corresponds to c^2 km² (also 1 S) of movement.

When this energy unit is compressed, it cannot move to create space, so it receives back the accumulated spatial value. This causes other objects to move. Thus, both gravity and expansion essentially increase spatial value. That is, they have the same nature and are not opposites.

4) Energy and Force

Thus, energy is the source that generates spatial value through its motion. And force is the way it generates spatial value. If energy does not directly create space (in the case of light), it will act on another object to create spatial value (force). Since that object has not yet reached the speed of light (spatial value c^2) the force increases its velocity, meaning that spatial value is gradually transferred from one system to another. The law of conservation of energy is actually the mechanism for conserving spatial value.

Thus, all concepts and laws of physics are also formed by the conservation, interaction, and mechanism of energy in motion that generates spatial value.

This is only a personal viewpoint that I would like to share from my own reflections. Thank you for reading these lines.